

REVALSEA

Operationalizing relational values for a more equitable
marine conservation

Data Management Plan

Version 1.0

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17196600](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17196600)

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101146373. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project information

Project number:	101146373
Project acronym:	REVALSEA
Project name:	Operationalizing relational values for a more equitable marine conservation
Due date	30/09/2025
Contact	Lazzari.natali@gmail.com
Author	Natali Lazzari
Contributors	Nicholas Murray; Sebastian Villasante

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Publication date	Change	Author
1.0	25.09.2025	Initial version	Natali Lazzari

Abstract

The global commitment to protect 30% of the oceans by 2030 faces several key challenges in preserving nature without exacerbating existing coastal resource conflicts. As ocean protection is rapidly increasing to halt biodiversity loss, we urgently need to understand why people value nature to better address these conflicts. The REVALSEA project will provide a novel theoretical approach and empirical evidence to quantify, predict, and integrate into marine conservation the diverse ways people express why they value their relationship with nature, i.e., relational values, in coastal systems. Relational values (RVs) emerge as a keystone in conservation efforts breaking with the traditional exclusively material valuation of nature and opening a new opportunity to adopt more inclusive and socially relevant strategies for biodiversity conservation. This aspect is rarely explored in marine systems, even when its consideration in conservation is critical to increase equity and reduce resource conflicts. Addressing RVs in marine conservation policies needs overcoming several intergenerational, methodological, and operational challenges. First, it must consider the intergenerational gap between what matters for those who influence decision-making (adults) and for those who have the potential to generate social-ecological changes (youth). Second, it requires the use of innovative interdisciplinary social-ecological research that integrates multidimensional datasets and uses novel machine learning technology to maximise data efficiency while minimising economic costs of data collection and analysis. Finally, it needs transdisciplinary cooperation with stakeholders and decision makers to co-generate specific recommendations for integrating RVs in conservation policies. REVALSEA will focus on the small-scale fisher's community in Spain as a case study to address all these challenges and develop a cutting-edge and globally scalable approach in other sociocultural contexts.

1. Introduction and purpose

The purpose of this Data Management Plan is to provide a detailed description of the procedures and protocols for managing the datasets generated throughout the lifetime of the REVALSEA project. This plan outlines the main data management principles, including data standards and metadata, sharing, archiving, preservation, and security.

This is a living document that will be regularly updated during the course of the project. It will be stored in the Zenodo repository under the name **REVALSEA_01_DMP_V1.0_WP4.pdf**

2. Data Summary

Types and formats of data used and generated by the project

REVALSEA aims to investigate why nature associated to coastal and marine systems is important for people. The project will generate data using a combination of qualitative methods ranging from the online distribution of surveys with sociodemographic and open questions (WP1), to the organization of participatory workshops (WP3). In addition, REVALSEA will re-use existing data that has already been published as open source in various national and global databases, such as [INE](#), [GBIF](#), and [Bio-ORACLE](#) (WP2). These secondary datasets will be employed to model the diversity of relational values and to train the predictive models. Apart from the scientific objectives, REVALSEA will generate material to disseminate its results to expert and no-expert audiences.

REVALSEA will generate data in various formats that will be accessible using free software. These formats are summarized in the table below.

Type of Data	Description	Format
Compressed data	Compression will be used for packaging files with similar and/or complementary content	.rar
Data bases and notes	Data produced from fieldwork by the researcher	.odt, .doc, .xlsx, .pdf
Codes and data	Storing and sharing data that are imported, processed and/or created in an R environment	.rdm (Rdata), .rda
Images	Images produced for scientific and dissemination purposes.	.jpg, .png
Videos	Videos produced for scientific and dissemination purposes.	.mp4
Reports	Scientific, technical, and dissemination purposes	.pdf
Presentations	Scientific and dissemination purposes.	.pdf, .ppt
Paper pre-prints	Green open access according to the H2020 guidelines	.pdf

REVALSEA will create and utilize data from various sources, including fieldwork (surveys), secondary data from different public databases (INE, GBIF, Bio-ORACLE), and communication materials (videos, preprints, presentations, journal articles, and reports). In the following tables, I provide a tentative summary of the different types of datasets that will be generated by REVALSEA, linked to the five work packages (WP) of the project. The total estimated amount of data is approximately 7 GB, with individual datasets ranging from 10 MB to 2,000 MB.

	Description of dataset	Type	Format	Quantity
WP1	To develop and operationalise a standardised tool for relational values (RVs) identification			
	Primary data from surveys	Excel table	.xlsx	< 500 MB
	Primary data from audio surveys	Audio	.mp3	< 1 GB
	Codes and data	Rdata	.rdm, .rda	< 20 MB
WP2	To develop an intergenerational-sensitive approach to spatially predict the diversity of RVs			
	Secondary data from public databases	Excel	.xlsx	< 200 MB
	Codes and data	Rdata	.rdm, .rda	< 20 MB
WP3	To collaboratively develop strategies for integrating RVs into conservation			
	Reports on the workshops conducted	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
	Pictures	Image	.jpg, .png	< 500 MB
	Videos	Video	.mp4	< 3 GB
WP4	Project management and career development plan			
	Career Development Plan	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
	DMP (including updates)	Report	.pdf	< 10 MB
	Reports on training conducted	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
WP5	Dissemination, exploitation, and communication			
	Dissemination and communication plan	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
	Final preprint versions of papers for expert audiences (Estimation: 3 preprints)	Paper preprint	.pdf	< 20 MB
	Press articles	Publication	.pdf	< 20 MB
	Infographics of the published articles	Image	.jpg, .png	< 200 MB
	Report on webpage and social media accounts	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
	Presentations in international conferences	Presentations	.rar	< 500 MB
	Presentations in internal seminars	Presentations	.rar	< 500 MB
	Presentations in events for non-expert audiences	Presentations	.rar	< 500 MB
	Funding proposals	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
	Open-access booklet	Booklet	.pdf	< 200 MB
	Briefing report	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB

Data utility

REVALSEA will advance coastal and marine social-ecological knowledge by empirically investigating the concept of RVs in coastal systems. This approach aims to prevent the blind implementation of the 30 by 30 initiative, which is likely to disproportionately affect minority groups and potentially exacerbate existing resource conflicts. Additionally, the project

responds to the current call for engagement with fundamental paradigms—considered “deep” leverage points—for transformational change in marine conservation. The data generated by REVALSEA will be relevant for various stakeholders, including policymakers, decision-makers, social organizations, and scholars involved in coastal and marine management. The outcomes of this three-and-a-half-year project will serve both as a precedent and a toolkit for integrating multiple values into marine conservation, providing European institutions and civil society with innovative mechanisms for social inclusion and the promotion of equitable management of coastal and marine social-ecological systems.

3. FAIR data

REVALSEA is fully committed to the FAIR principles. In this regard, I have planned several actions aimed at maximizing the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reproducibility of the data and results that I will generate during the project.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data archived during REVALSEA will be associated with a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) to ensure unambiguous identification. Additionally, data files will be assigned intuitive dataset identifiers, created according to the convention outlined in the table below.

Convention for creating the Dataset Identifier	
Components	Example
Project name	REVALSEA (always)
Title of the dataset	PresentationIMPAC6
Version of the dataset (Zenodo will allow to keep several versions)	V1.0
Work Package associated to the dataset	WP5
Format of the dataset	ppt

Example dataset file identifier: REVALSEA_PresentationIMPAC6_V1.0_WP5.ppt

Archived data will be accompanied by detailed metadata (in text or PDF format), which will be updated as necessary and will include the information outlined in the table below. I will ensure that metadata is publicly and openly accessible. To compile the metadata, I will use search keywords to facilitate cross-referencing information across different data files.

Contents of a generic Metadata file associated to a given Dataset	
Dataset Identifier	The ID will result from the naming convention provided in the previous table
Title of the Dataset	The title of the dataset, which will be easily searchable and findable
Work Package	Project work package
Dataset Description	A brief description of the dataset
Dataset Dissemination	Where will the dataset be disseminated (e.g. peer reviewed journal)

Type Format	See table with formats in Data Summary section
Expected Size	Dataset size (see size in the Data Summary section)
Source	How was the dataset generated (e.g. surveys)
Repository	Zenodo
DOI (if known)	The DOI will be entered once the dataset has been deposited
Date of Submission	The date of submission will be added once the dataset has been uploaded on the repository
Keywords	Keywords associated with the dataset
Version Number	Version number to keep track of changes

I will make the metadata available in a form that can be harvested and indexed. In this regard, if I modify the content of the metadata, I will update the creation date accordingly. This will ensure that the metadata are versioned and kept current.

3.2. Making data accessible

Repository

I will release the data and associated metadata in Zenodo, a trusted repository developed and operated by CERN and the OpenAIRE project, which is funded by the European Commission (more information at <https://zenodo.org>). This repository offers versioning of archived data and scripts and links each dataset to a unique DOI.

Data

The data hosted in the Zenodo repository will be accessible to the entire research community under the CC-BY license. In this regard, the data generated by REVALSEA do not involve any intellectual property rights, such as patents, trademarks, or copyrights. Data produced within REVALSEA will not be subject to embargo and will be made available immediately. No "data access committee" will be required to regulate data requests related to REVALSEA.

Access to the open data deposited in Zenodo does not require any specialized methods or software tools. The files can be downloaded from the repository using a standard web browser. The software and tools needed for viewing, interpreting, or further processing the data files depend on their type and format (see Data Summary section), but they are generally available in common text or numeric formats (e.g., .xlsx, .pdf, etc.). Data will be stored in formats compatible with open-source software and programming languages, such as RStudio.

3.3. Making data interoperable

REVALSEA aims to collect and document all data generated in a standardized manner to ensure that all datasets, accompanied by their respective metadata files, can be properly interpreted and shared.

All data formats used within REVALSEA (see Data Summary section), with the exception of RData, can be imported and reused in various software. RData files are specific to the R environment, which may limit their usability. However, R is currently one of the most widely used open-source software for data analysis within the research community.

Any new data generated within REVALSEA (e.g., text documents or matrix-like objects) will be produced using the same data formats outlined in the Data Summary section.

3.4. Increase data re-use

Research data generated from the REVALSEA project will be made available for reuse simultaneously with the publication of the corresponding scientific paper, which will be open access. Open results will be released under a Creative Commons license (CC BY), providing a legal framework for permitting open access and reuse.

The data will remain reusable after the conclusion of the project, with no time limitations or access restrictions.

When necessary, I will include a README file associated with the datasets, providing additional information such as details on methodology, data cleaning, analyses, or variable definitions.

4. Allocation of resources

There are no immediate costs associated with making REVALSEA research data FAIR. In particular, no costs are foreseen for the immediate and long-term storage of open results in the project's default repository (Zenodo). However, providing open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications may require payment of Article Processing Charges (APCs).

Any costs related to open access to research data and publications in Horizon 2020 are eligible for reimbursement during the project duration, under the conditions outlined in the Grant Agreement, and will be covered by the project's budget.

As part of the training and development of transferable and complementary skills conducted under Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions – Individual Fellowships (MSCA-IF), Dr. Natali Lazzari has assumed responsibilities for data management within the project. She will also be responsible for creating the Data Management Plan (DMP), updating it as needed, and maintaining the datasets generated by REVALSEA.

5. Data security

The potential impact on the project if information is lost, leaked, or vandalized is minimal. Data generated within REVALSEA will be stored in a secure repository (Zenodo) that adheres to the highest standards of data security. Zenodo servers are managed in accordance with the CERN Security Baseline for Servers (more information at: <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>).

6. Ethics

As REVALSEA involves conducting research with vulnerable communities, specifically young small-scale fishers, I will pay particular attention to ensuring respect for these communities and the protection of vulnerable participants within the research plans. Following the recommendation of European Commission ethics experts, an ethics mentor from the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC, the host institution) will be appointed and consulted throughout the project. This mentor will assist in identifying and recruiting research participants and provide ongoing guidance during the implementation of REVALSEA.

Additionally, the survey designed to gather relevant information will require approval from the USC ethics committee prior to distribution. All current ethical considerations related to the REVALSEA project will comply with the EU's key ethical principles, research codes of conduct, and applicable regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (No. 2016/679). While personal information will be anonymized before sharing, informed consent forms will include clauses regarding data sharing and long-term preservation to enable open data practices.

The ethics mentor will also guide the researcher in adopting an ethically responsible approach to the development and application of machine learning predictive techniques (in WP2) and will direct the researcher to the European Commission's guidelines on ethics in AI-based solutions.

7. Other issues

Currently, the project does not utilize any other national, funder, sectorial, or departmental procedures for data management.